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TEST BENCHES FOR TESTING DETECTING MATERIALS IN PICOSECOND AND SUB-PICOSECOND DOMAINS

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Abstract:

For characterization of the fast timing properties of scintillating materials, several test benches have been developed and commissioned in various institutes within WP8 task 8.3.1 such as time resolved spectroscopy with pulsed Xrays, time coincidence resolution, pump and probe, test beam set-up for assessing the timing performances using high energy particles in beam tests. A description of the different benches is given in this document.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2022

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

For characterization of the fast timing properties of scintillating materials, several test benches have been developed and commissioned in various institutes within WP8 task 8.3.1. These include set-up for decay time measurements (time resolved spectroscopy with pulsed Xrays), time resolution measurements under various types of excitations, for transient absorption measurements and test beam set-ups for assessing the timing performances using high energy particles in beam tests. The benches are operational and used for first measurements

1. INTRODUCTION

Activities of AIDAinnova WP8 focus on the development of calorimeters and particle identification detectors for future experiment in high energy physics (HEP). Light based detectors are potential technology studied in the task 8.3. Future detectors in HEP required radiation hard scintillating materials with ultrafast timing response. To reach a time resolution better than 30ps a deep understanding of the scintillating mechanisms is needed and therefore the availability of instrumentation able to assess timing performances is important. For this purpose, several test set-ups have been developed in the frame of subtask 8.3.1 in various partners. The availability of these various test set-ups provides a unique infrastructure for a deep understanding of timing properties of scintillating materials.

The description of the different available benches is presented in the following sections.

2. TEST BENCHES @CERN

Several benches to characterise the timing properties of scintillating materials have been developed at CERN: time resolution set-ups under various excitation as well as radioluminescence decay spectra.

2.1. COINCIDENCE TIME RESOLUTION SETUP WITH 511KEV

2.1.1. Description of Coincidence time resolution setup

Coincidence time resolution (CTR) upon 511 keV gamma excitation is measured with the bench [1], illustrated in figure 1. A ^{22}Na source is placed between two crystals under test. These crystals are by default wrapped in Teflon and glued to Silicon Photomultipliers (SiPMs). Custom made electronics is used to monitor the voltage drop between the SiPM anode and cathode. The signal is split, where one signal part is amplified with an operational amplifier (AD8000) to have a good information on the deposited energy, while the other part is processed by a Balun Transformer and a cascade of two RF-amplifiers (detailed description in [1]). The signals of both detector arms are digitized with a LeCroy DDA 735 Zi oscilloscope (3.5 GHz bandwidth, 20Gs/s sampling rate). For the time information a leading edge (typically below the amplitude of a single SiPM cell signal) is set on the oscilloscope of the high frequency (HF) signal, while the energy information is obtained via integration of the signal being amplified by the operational amplifier.

The data analysis (eg. selection of 511keV photopeak events, fitting of the coincidence time delay distribution) is done offline with ROOT.

Figure 1: Picture of CTR setup with digitized scintillation pulses and energy spectrum

The setup is capable to work in several modes: Apart from standard scintillating crystals it can also be used for novel materials such as nanomaterials.

2.1.2. Example CTR measurements

In figure 2 examples of a measured charge histogram and time delay histogram obtained with the set-up are presented.

Figure 2: (left) Normalized histogram of measured charge for a pure Cherenkov radiator with different crystal surface condition. (right) Coincidence time delay distribution of two BGO crystals.

2.1.3. Timing measurements with high energy MIPs

A similar setup based on time resolution measurements may be employed for test beam measurements. Crystals are coupled to SiPMs and read out with similar electronics, a beam of high energy particles (electrons, muons, pions) passing through the two crystals. A picture of the setup is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Picture of test-beam setup. The beam is coming from the left side.

The samples show a strong linear correlation between time delay and signal amplitude (deposited energy), therefore a time-walk correction was performed. This is done with a linear fit function of the scattered plot between time and energy, and the corrected time stamp is thus

$t_{cor} = t - f(\text{amplitude})$, improving significantly the time resolution. An example of a measurement with and without time walk correction (TWC) on a reference crystal is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Coincidence time delay distribution of a LSO crystal against the timestamp produced from MCP-PMTs.

2.2. TIMING SETUP WITH X-RAYS AND SiPMs

While nanomaterial-based scintillators like CdSe, InGaN or CsPbBr₃ have the potential to deliver an ultrafast time response, the scintillation characteristics is difficult to investigate with standard methods due to the low interaction probability. In order to overcome this issue, a setup based on an X-ray tube in combination with SiPMs has been developed, allowing to simultaneously determine the time response (coincidence time resolution with laser trigger) and light output (number of detected photons).

2.2.1. Description of the Setup with X-rays

A pulsed diode laser (PDL 800-B, PicoQuant) triggers the production of X-ray photons with energy of up to 40keV (mean energy 9keV, XRT N5084 Hamamatsu). The X-rays interact with the sample under test, which is glued to a SiPM and read out by custom electronics [1].

By integrating the SiPM signal and calibration, the light output of the sample is determined. An illustration of the operating principle is shown in figure 5.

By comparing the time difference of the SiPM signal with respect to the laser trigger, a coincidence time spectrum is plotted, allowing to determine the detector time resolution (DTR) of the sample.

Figure 5: Measurement principle for DTR and light output characterization upon X-ray excitation

2.2.2. Example timing and light output measurements with X-rays

An example of the light output measurement is shown on the left of figure 6 for two different samples. Since X-rays can also interact with only the SiPM and produce a signal, the response of only the SiPM is also evaluated. An example time resolution measurement is shown on the right of figure 6.

Figure 6: (left) Example light output measurement of nano-based materials with μm thick active layer (InGaN Multiple Quantum Well). (right): Example time resolution measurement upon X-ray (mean 9keV) excitation.

2.3. TIME CORRELATED SINGLE PHOTON COUNTING MEASUREMENT WITH X-RAY AND 511KEV GAMMA EXCITATION

In order to investigate scintillation kinetics as well as to explore other light production mechanisms (cross luminescence, hot intraband luminescence, quantum confinement, Cherenkov emission) with rise and decay time measurements, two test benches have been developed. Both are based on the time correlated single photon counting method, but they differ on the excitation energy (either 511keV gammas or X-rays with ~10keV) giving unique features [2,3]).

2.3.1. Description of TCSPC setups

The working principle of both setups are shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: (left) Working principle of TCSPC setup with 511keV gamma excitation adapted from [2], (right) Working principle with X-ray excitation.

511keV excitation

A ^{22}Na source is placed between a reference detector and a crystal under test. The start signal is produced by the detection of a 511keV gamma in the reference detector. The crystal under test is placed on top of a SiPM, which is used to monitor the energy deposited in the material. The stop signal is given by a photon avalanche diode (ID-Quantique (IDQ)). An optical filter can be placed between crystal under test and the stop detector to select on certain wavelengths.

The signal of both detector arms is digitized with Lecroy Oscilloscope (1GHz bandwidth, 10Gs/s sampling rate). The raw waveforms are saved and offline analysed with MATLAB.

The impulse response function (IRF) of the setup depends on the start detector and the geometry of the crystal under test (a large crystal introduces additional photon time spread) but can be directly measured using a Cherenkov radiator with similar geometry. For a small reference detector, the IRF is well described by a Gaussian with 52 ps standard deviation [4].

X-ray excitation

A pulsed laser is used to drive the X-ray Tube and trigger the production of X-rays which excite the sample under test. Instead of the IDQ, a hybrid PMT (HPT) is used to detect the photons produced from the sample under test. The coincidence time delay between the laser trigger and the signal of the hybrid PMT is stored.

The IRF of the system is partly measured (laser + HPT) while the jitter contribution from the X-ray tube is provided by Hamamatsu. Convoluting both contributions lead to an overall function with tails and FWHM of 180ps.

For both setups it is essential that the stop detector (IDQ or hybrid PMT) operates in single photon counting mode, hence for each interaction the probability that one photon is detected is very low. Only this way the scintillation kinetics can be properly reconstructed.

The scintillation time profile is mathematically described with a multi component bi-exponential function. The data is fitted convoluting the function with the IRF and the analysis is done with MATLAB.

$$f(t|\theta) = \rho_i \cdot \Theta(t - \theta) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{t-\theta}{\tau_{d,i}}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{t-\theta}{\tau_{r,i}}\right)}{\tau_{d,i} - \tau_{r,i}}$$

where $\tau_{d,i}$ $\tau_{r,i}$ ρ_i are respectively the decay time, the rise time and the relative abundance of the i^{th} component, θ the start time of the scintillation process, and $\Theta(t)$ the Heaviside step function.

2.3.2. Example TCSPC measurement

An example of a radioluminescence decay spectrum is presented on figure 8

Figure 8: Rise and decay time measurement of CsPbBr₃ upon X-ray excitation

3. TEST BENCH @ IP-ASCR

3.1. DESCRIPTION

Radioluminescence decays with picosecond resolution are measured by the common TCSPC method (Time-Correlated Single Photon Counting). The decay curves are collected using the hybrid picosecond photon detector HPPD-860 operating in 220-860 nm spectral range and coupled with a Fluorohub-A-Plus controller (Horiba Scientific). Samples are excited by the X-ray tube N5084 (Hamamatsu), operating at 40 kV. The X-ray tube is driven by the light pulser equipped with a laser diode operating at 405 nm (Hamamatsu), fig. 9. The instrumental response function FWHM of the setup is about 71 ps. An example of the raw measurement is presented in fig. 10. A convolution

procedure is applied to the decay curves to determine the true decay times (SpectraSolve software package, Ames Photonics). The measurements are usually performed using a reflection configuration (emission is detected from the same surface where excited). The resolution of the measurement, even for the rise times, is of about few tens of picoseconds only. An example of the elaborated scintillation decay of GaN-InGaN multiple quantum well is shown in fig. 11.

Fig. 9. View of the IP-ASCR setup inside the experimental chamber. Left to right: laser with focusing lens and mirror; X-ray tube; sample holder; detector.

Fig. 10. Screenshot of the decay curve measurement using dedicated software.

3.2. EXAMPLE OF MEASUREMENTS

Fig. 11 An example of the elaboration and fit of the scintillation decay of GaN/InGaN multiple quantum well.

4. TEST BENCH @ VILNIUS FOR CHARACTERIZATION OF SCINTILLATOR TIMING PROPERTIES

4.1. BENCH DESCRIPTION

The bench enables in parallel measuring the scintillator characteristics obtained by photoluminescence spectroscopy with a time resolution of 200 ps and by transient optical absorption technique with a time resolution in the sub-picosecond domain. The schematic outline of the test bench with just the main component shown and the list of its capabilities and key functional parameters are presented in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12. Schematic outline of the test bench and the list of its capabilities and key functional parameters

4.2. DEMONSTRATION OF CAPABILITIES

The bench is tested by performing measurements on three Ce-doped gadolinium gallium garnet (GAGG:Ce) scintillator single crystal co-doped with different amounts of magnesium. Photoluminescence spectra and kinetics of the samples are presented in Fig. 413.

Fig. 13. Photoluminescence spectra (a) and kinetics (b) of three GAGG:Ce with different Mg co-doping

Figure 14. presents the initial data carpet: the intensity of the transient absorption in terms of excitation-induced optical density (see color scale) as a function of the probe photon energy and the delay between monochromatic pump and white-light probe pulses (200 fs in duration).

Fig. 14. Data carpet of Transient absorption measurement (a) and decay kinetics extracted from the carpet (b)

Fig. 15. Initial part of TA response in GAGG:Ce,Mg

The results on the study of the rising part of the transient absorption are illustrated in Fig. 15, where the rise times defined as the time period between the TA signal peak position and the point corresponding to 5% of the peak value (indicated in the plot) in three GAGG:Ce,Mg studied are presented in the table. The result demonstrates the capability to characterize the leading edge of the TA response with sub-picosecond accuracy.

4.3. VALIDATION

Fig. 16. Results of repeatability test

The time resolution in photoluminescence measurements is limited at 200 ps by the time correlated single photon counter, whereas the time resolution in TA measurements is limited just by the pulse width of 250 fs.

The repeatability of the measurements is tested by repeating the measurements a few months later, after the setup has been disassembled and reassembled. Thin and thick lines in Fig. 16 represent the transient absorption kinetics obtained in the two measurements for the same spectral positions indicated in the figure. The measurements demonstrate a good long-term repeatability of the results.

5. TEST BENCH @ INFN PERUGIA FOR LIGHT OUTPUT AND TIMING MEASUREMENTS

The laboratory in INFN-PG have developed test benches to characterize light output and decay time of crystals with different readout options.

5.1. BENCH DESCRIPTION

A black box can allocate crystals as long as 30 cm, where the signal is triggered by a pair of scintillator fingers. Front End electronics has been developed and assembled to read out Avalanche Photodiodes (APD) using a CREMAT preamplifier CR110, or Silicon Photomultipliers (SiPM) with a custom-made filter plus amplifier. The test bench allows to read out one crystal with APD and SiPM at the same time in order to compare the results. Figure 17 shows a crystal connected to the box containing the CREMAT preamplifier (view from the top and from the back). The second box contains the filter for the SiPM readout.

Figure 17: Crystal connected to the box containing the CREMAT preamplifier and filter board for the SiPM readout.

5.2. EXAMPLE OF MEASUREMENTS

Measurements of the signal after the amplifier have been performed; an example of the waveform and of the signal amplitude after pedestal subtraction is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Example of a collected waveform (left) and of the signal amplitude after pedestal subtraction (right).

The shaping of the signal can be performed in two different ways with a software shaping or designing and assembling a shaping board. Both of these options are under study and will be developed in the next months.

Pure CsI crystals and CsI(Tl) are available for the test, to compare light output and decay time. Some samples of LaBr₃ have been ordered from the Saint Gobain company and will be tested as soon as they will be available.

A setup with a cryostat system, which can allocate only small samples 1x1x1 cm³, has also been assembled in order to measure the increase of light output in pure CsI crystal at cryogenic temperature.

6. TEST BENCH @ INFN FRASCATTI AND TORINO: PLATFORM FOR BEAM TEST MEASUREMENTS OF TIME RESOLUTION FOR CRYSTAL CALORIMETER COMPONENTS AND SMALL PROTOTYPES

To complement measurements of scintillation properties in the picosecond and sub-picosecond ranges carried out at the test bench facilities of the other partners, the INFN Frascati and Torino collaborators are developing techniques for the measurement of the timing properties of crystal calorimeter components and small prototypes at test beam facilities. This provides important feedback information to assist in the extrapolation of test bench measurements to estimate the potential for instruments constructed with candidate detector materials to achieve 30 ps time resolution in the real world.

6.1. TEST BENCH SETUP AT THE FRASCATI BEAM-TEST FACILITY

A first test-bench setup was established at the Beam-Test Facility (BTF) at INFN Frascati in summer 2021. In dedicated running, the BTF can provide electron beams of 25-700 MeV of intensity from 1 to 10^{10} particles per 1.5-40 ns spill at a repetition rate of 10-50 Hz. The ability to run in single-electron mode is especially useful for instrument testing. Typical values of the beam spot size and beam divergence are 10 mm and 1 mrad, respectively, with optimum values obtained for beam energies of around 500 MeV. The beam profile can be monitored using a $15 \times 15 \text{ mm}^2$ FitPIX 55 μm silicon pixel array that is part of the BTF infrastructure. The setup used for the study of candidate calorimeter crystals is shown in Fig. 19, in which are visible the beam exit window, the BTF FitPIX beam monitor, and the sample holder (CRILIN module 0) mounted on a vertical and horizontal motion stage.

Figure 19: Test bench setup at the Frascati BTF. Left: The BTF-1 and BTF-2 beamlines. The summer 2021 tests were carried out with beam extracted in the straight section of BTF-1, shown by the red line. Right: Detail of beam exit, with FitPIX detector and PbF2 crystal samples in position (CRILIN module 0).

The first measurements were carried out with this setup in parasitic data taking in the straight section of the BTF-1 beamline during BTF-2 commissioning in July 2021. The samples to be studied were two 10x10x40 mm PbF₂ crystals (SICCAS, Shanghai). These were mounted in and read out with the CRILIN module 0 prototype developed for the Muon Collider experiment. For each crystal, the Cerenkov light was read out with a 2x2 array of Hamamatsu S14160-4050HS SiPMs (50 μm pixel size, 4x4 mm² sensitive area) in two channels, each with the analog sum of the signals from two of the SiPMs. An existing SiPM front-end was used with amplifiers with selectable gain (x1, x10) and shaping to 100 ns fall time. The signals were digitized with a 2.5 GS/s LeCroy WaveSurfer HDO6104 oscilloscope with 1 GHz bandwidth. The crystals were exposed to 450 MeV electron beams from the BTF and the time resolution was measured as a function of deposited energy from the difference of measured times between the independent readout channels from the same crystal. A variety of signal analysis techniques were applied. Analysis of the data is still in progress. For future measurements with this test bench, we will work in the new BTF-2 user beamline. The reference time signal will be obtained with the MCP-PMT tagger described below.

6.2. TEST-BENCH SETUP AT THE CERN SPS NORTH AREA

A second test-bench setup was established in the CERN H2 beamline in August 2021 (Figure 20). The setup, which was assembled with the help of collaborators from the University of Insubria (Como, Italy) and INFN Milano Bicocca, is illustrated in Fig. 21. Secondary hadron and muon beams and high-purity tertiary electron beams can be delivered in H2. The setup shown in Fig. 21 was designed to allow measurements with 20-120 GeV electrons and tagged photons produced with 120 GeV electron beams. The instrumented crystal (or small prototype) is positioned on a 2-axis rotation and 2-axis translation stage at the point GC. The beam is incident from the left. S1-S2 are scintillators to define the fiducial beam section and generate the trigger; the beam particles are tracked in silicon strip detectors T1, T2 (2x2 cm², 50 μm pitch) and BC1 (9x9 cm², 242 μm pitch). The time reference was obtained from the coincidence of signals of beam particles in Cerenkov radiators viewed by two 18-mm MCP-PMTs (Katod LLP UFK-5G-2D). For data taking with photon beam, a copper target of 1 mm thickness (7% X₀) is used to produce bremsstrahlung photons, and a 4 T·m dipole magnet (MBPL, shown by the triangle) was used to deviate the beam electron into an array of lead-glass calorimeter modules (eCAL), tagging the presence of the forward photon and providing a measurement of the electron energy, while a BGO calorimeter directly measures the transmitted photon energy. S3 and S4 are scintillator paddles, the former to assist in discriminating events in which the incident particle is an electron or a photon, and the latter, together with the silicon strip detector BC2 (same properties as BC1), provides a measurement of the charged particle multiplicity produced in the interaction with the crystal. For data taking with electrons, the target is removed, the magnet is turned off, and the beam is incident directly on the crystal at GC. With this setup, light production by the crystals can be studied as a function of alignment of the crystallographic axis with respect to the direction of incident particles, as expected due to modifications to the sample response from the coherent interactions of beam particles with the crystal lattice.

Figure 90: Schematic diagram of the test-bench in the CERN H2 beam line.

Samples tested in August 2021 included the PbF_2 crystals tested in July and a single PbF_2 crystal (also from SICCAS) with dimensions $10 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$ and known orientation of the $\langle 110 \rangle$ axis. The crystals were mounted in the CRILIN module 0 prototype with light readout as described above. With a modified setup, an oriented PWO-II crystal of dimensions $30 \times 30 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$ was also tested. All signals, from both the SiPMs and the MCP-PMTs, were digitized at 2.5 GHz with CAEN DT5742 digitizers. The samples were exposed to electron beams of energy 20-120 GeV, tagged photon beams derived from the 120 GeV electron beam, and 150 GeV muon beams. Figure 21 shows the PbF_2 crystals mounted in the CRILIN module on the rotation stage undergoing alignment on the H2 test bench in August 2021.

Figure 22: PbF_2 crystals being aligned with the beam on the H2 test bench.

The time resolution studies are in progress; a variety of signal analysis techniques have been used. From the difference of measured times with the MCP-PMTs, we obtain a resolution for the time

reference signal at the level of 20 ps. The analysis of the signals from the SiPMs is more difficult due to the longer signal duration; the stochastic contribution to the time resolution for the PbF₂ crystals is seen to be less than 100 ps, but this analysis is still in progress.

6.3. FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

A demonstration module for the CRILIN calorimeter/KLEVER small-angle calorimeter (SAC) based on the above principles is under development and will serve as an improved platform for these test beam measurements. The experience gained in 2021 has led to various optimizations for our 2022 test beam proposal. In particular, a two-layer crystal array with 3x3 crystals per layer (10x10x40 mm³) will be used: this will provide some degree of shower containment and allow information on transverse and longitudinal shower development to be obtained. The time resolution can then be obtained for calorimeter clusters. This setup can be used to evaluate the performance of various crystal candidates. In 2022 we will perform two tests: one with both layers populated with PbF₂ crystals from SICCAS, and one in which the first layer is populated with PWO-III crystals from Crytur. In both cases, the crystallographic axis of the central crystal on the first layer will be aligned with the beam for tests of the response as a function of angle of incidence. Importantly, the light will be read out with faster SiPMs (Hamamatsu S14160-3015PS, 15 μm, 3x3 mm²) and faster electronics (signal shaping with 3 ns rise time and 70 ns fall time). One week of beam time has been requested at the H2 beam line in summer 2022, and additional running is foreseen in 2022 at the BTF, as well as in subsequent years.

7. CONCLUSION

Several benches of the light output and scintillation characterization are now available in different partner institutes to understand the fundamental mechanism of scintillation needed to the optimization of the scintillating material and for the evaluation the performances of prototype detectors based on the developed materials.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] S. Gundacker, R. M. Turtos, E. Auffray, M. Paganoni, P. Lecoq , High-frequency SiPM readout advances measured coincidence time resolution limits in TOF-PET, Phys. Med. Biol 64 (2019) 055012, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6560/aafd52>
- [2] S. Gundacker, E. Auffray, K. Pauwels, P. Lecoq , Measurement of intrinsic rise times for various L(Y)SO and LuAG scintillators with a general study of prompt photons to achieve 10 ps in TOF-PET, Phys. Med. Biol 61(2016) 2802, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0031-9155/61/7/2802>
- [3] S. Gundacker, R. M. Turtos, E. Auffray, P. Lecoq Precise rise and decay time measurements of inorganic scintillators by means of X-ray and 511 keV excitation, NIM A 891 (2018) 42–52, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2018.02.074>
- [4] L. Martinazzoli, N. Kratochwil, S. Gundacker, E. Auffray: Scintillation properties and timing performance of state-of-the-art $Gd_3Al_2Ga_3O_{12}$ single crystals, NIM A 1000 (2021)165231, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2021.165231>

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
APD	Avalanche Photodiodes
BTF	Beam Test Facility
CTR	Coincidence Time Resolution
DTR	Detector Time Resolution
FWHM	Full width half maximum
HEP	High Energy Physics
HF	High Frequency
HPT	Hybrid Photomultiplier Tube
HPPD	Hybrid Picosecond Photon Detector
IDQ	ID-Quantique
IRF	Impulse Response Function
MCP-PMT	Micro Channel Plate Photomultiplier Tube
PDL	Pulsed Diode Laser
SiPM	Silicon Photomultipliers
TA	Transient Absorption
TCSPC	Time Correlated Single Photon Counting
TWC	Time Walk Correction